

Donatism

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The Donatist controversy erupted in early fourth century Roman North Africa in the immediate aftermath of the Diocletianic persecution. The North African church was heir to the legacy of Cyprian of Carthage, whose belief that lapsed bishops were ineligible to administer the sacraments would prove crucial in the events that followed. During the Diocletianic persecution, a rift developed within the church over the status of bishops who had complied with the authorities and handed over their copies of the scriptures to be burned, an action referred to as traditio. In response to rumors that the newly-elected bishop of Carthage, a man named Caecilian, had been ordained by such a compromised bishop, a group of seventy bishops from Numidia denounced his ordination as illegitimate and elevated an alternate candidate to the Carthaginian bishopric. After their candidate was rejected at the councils of Rome in 313 and Arles in 314, the dissidents, called "Donatists" by their opponents after their charismatic second leader, Donatus of Carthage, were considered schismatic by the wider Christian church. Within Roman North Africa proper (modern Tunisia, Algeria, and parts of Morocco), congregations that viewed Donatus and his successors as the legitimate bishops of Carthage seem to have been in the majority throughout the fourth century. Failed repressions by the emperors Constantine in the 320s and Constans in the late 340s created a strong self-narrative among the dissidents that theirs was the church that "suffers persecution but does not cause it" (Gesta Carth. 3.258), though violent reprisals by Donatist partisans known as Circumcellions against their Caecilianist opponents tarnished this claim. Despite their "schismatic" status, Donatist writers were influential among Latin Christian communities outside of North Africa, especially the maverick theologian Tyconius, whose Book of Rules and Commentary on the Apocalypse dominated Western Christian approaches to exegesis and eschatology well into the Carolingian era. The Cyprianic position that schismatic bishops could not legitimately perform the sacraments led many Donatist communities to require converts from the rival church to be baptized upon entry, a practice their opponents decried as "rebaptism." The decline of the dissident communion can be attributed in large part to the efforts of Caecilianist opponents like Augustine of Hippo and Aurelius of Carthage in the 390s, which culminated in an imperial edict in 405 imposing heavy fines and confiscation of property on adherents. This edict was reaffirmed in 411 at an imperially-sanctioned debate between the two sides at Carthage. Donatism survived as a coherent movement long after the Vandal invasion of the 430s, and was last referenced as a contemporary phenomenon in the letters of Pope Gregory I late in the sixth century.

Date Range: 311 CE - 600 CE

Region: Donatist North Africa

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Carthage

Extent of the Donatist church in fourth-century North Africa based on bishop-list at the 411 Conference at Carthage

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Shaw, Brent. 2011. *Sacred Violence: African Christians and Sectarian Hatred in the Age of Augustine*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Source 2: Tilley, Maureen. 1997. *The Bible in Christian North Africa: The Donatist World*. Minneapolis: Fortress Press.
- Source 3: Frend, W.H.C. 1952. *The Donatist Church: A Movement of Protest in Roman North Africa*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://donatism.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Online dynamic bibliography of texts related to Donatist studies.
- Source 2 URL: <https://earlychurch.org.uk/donatism.php>
- Source 2 Description: Brief overview of Donatist history and thought.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf104.html>
- Source 1 Description: An English translation of several of Augustine of Hippo's Anti-Donatist writings.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.tertullian.org/fathers/optatus_00_eintro.htm
- Source 2 Description: An English translation of Optatus of Milevis, *Against the Donatists*.
- Source 3 URL: http://www.seanmultimedia.com/Pie_Petilian_Encyclical_Letter.html
- Source 3 Description: An online transcription of a Donatist encyclical letter by Petilian of Cirta

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Children born to Donatist parents were probably baptized soon after birth.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Donatist adherents would have undergone the rite of baptism. If they had previously been members of an opposing Christian sect, they would be "rebaptized," as Donatists did not accept the validity of outside baptisms.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

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↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: While sometimes tolerated in Roman North Africa, Donatist Christians endured periods of state persecution throughout the fourth and fifth centuries.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

Notes: By the late 390s, Donatist Christians, in particular members of the clergy, who converted to the rival Christian sect in North Africa could be targeted by fanatical mobs and mutilated or forced to flee.

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Donatists believed that apostates were outside the true church and were thus in danger of damnation.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Donatists were able to field 288 bishops at the 411 Conference at Carthage, indicating a broad base of public support (Shaw, *Sacred Violence*, 570). Estimates of the total population of Roman North Africa in late antiquity range from 4 million to 8 million, the majority of whom would have been Christian by the end of the fourth century. Donatists seem to have been numerically superior to their rivals up to the early fifth century.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While no precise percentages can be given, the ratio of bishops present at the 411 Conference at Carthage is informative. Donatists were able to produce 288 bishops, while their rivals fielded 286 (Shaw, *Sacred Violence*, 570-571).

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: As a rule, Donatist bishops were not considered charismatic. However, legends appear to have been told about miracles worked by Donatus of Carthage and associates: cf. Augustine, *Tract. Ev. Io. 13.17.1*.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Notes: Donatist leaders were considered heretics by Roman emperors such as Constantine, Constans, and Honorius.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Donatists would have held the same assumptions about the divine inspiration of the Christian canon as their opponents.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Production of Latin translations of the Bible seems to have been haphazard, and multiple recensions of the Old Latin are known.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Donatists adhered to the same biblical canon as their Christian rivals, though they were noticeably more conservative about excluding some disputed texts, such as the book of Hebrews.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Donatists built basilicas for worship alongside their Christian rivals. These basilicas are virtually indistinguishable from each other, and both sides frequently took over the other's for their own use.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Donatist basilica at Timgad, one of the few surviving structures that can be traced back to the movement, is 200 feet long by 50 feet across.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Donatist monumental architecture was confined to the production of basilicas for their congregations. Few examples survive.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Notes: Donatist iconography is virtually identical to their Christian rivals. Both sides used common Christian tropes when decorating their basilicas.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Donatist pilgrimages to martyr sites such as Nova Petra, the mountain from which bishop Marculus was allegedly thrown from, from are known from primary sources.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Informal pilgrimages to martyr shrines seem to have been relatively common in Roman North Africa by both Donatists and their rivals. Many of these sites were considered sacred to both sides, though specifically-Donatist martyr shrines are known from primary sources.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– I don't know

- ↳ Other grave goods:
 - Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

- ↳ As cenotaphs:
 - Yes

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Family tomb-crypt:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
 - Yes [specify]: Bishops and martyrs often interred within basilica.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Donatists appear to have agreed with the developing Nicene theological tradition regarding the trinitarian characteristics of the Christian God.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: A Donatist text titled *Prophetiae ex omnibus libris collectae* specifies seven ways that revelation can be mediated from God to humans: ecstasy, visions, dreams, through a cloud, a voice from heaven, oracles, and

being filled with the Holy Spirit

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - I don't know

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Like all Christians of late antiquity, Donatists believed in angelic beings in the service of God.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - I don't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - I don't know

- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

- ↳ Adultery:

– Yes

- ↳ Incest:

– Yes

- ↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Donatists would have mirrored early Christian sexual ethics.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:
– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– I don't know

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - Yes

- ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other purpose:
 - I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Some Donatist partisans called "Circumcellions" by their opponents were accused of suicidal behavior as part of a desire for martyrdom.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Like other Christians in late antiquity, tithing and charitable giving was expected.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Some Donatist partisans, called Circumcellions by their opponents, were known for taking physical risks in their desire to achieve martyrdom.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– I don't know

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– I don't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: While an "institutionalized police force" is anachronistic for the Donatist church, members did interact both positively and negatively with the Roman legions charged with keeping the peace in North Africa.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as bishops judged local cases in their dioceses.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Donatist bishops were not officially recognized by the state, though at times they allied with local leaders to enforce ecclesiastical violations.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Donatists would have employed a rudimentary canon law system similar to their rivals. "Canon law" as such, however, was not a fully developed concept at this time period.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Donatist partisans known as the "Circumcellions" at times functioned like a paramilitary arm of the movement, but were not institutionalized.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Like all inhabitants of Roman North Africa, Donatists were protected by Roman military units stationed primarily on the frontier.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Maureen Tilley. "Dilatory Donatists or Procrastinating Catholics: The Trial at the Conference of Carthage". *Church History*, 60(1)

Reference: Brent Shaw. "Who Were the Circumcellions?". (Brent Shaw, A. H. Merrills, Ed.), *Vandals, Romans, and Berbers: New Perspectives on Late Antique North Africa*. Variorum. isbn: 978-0754641452.

Reference: Richard Rouse , Charles McNelis. "North African literary activity: A Cyprian fragment, the stichometric lists and a Donatist compendium."

Reference: Éric Rebillard. *Christians and their Many Identities in Late Antiquity: North Africa, 200-450*. Cornell University Press. isbn: 978-0801451423.

Reference: Aaron Pelttari. "Donatist Self-Identity and the 'Church of the Truth'". *Augustinianum*, 49(2)

Reference: Peter Kaufman. "Donatism Revisited: Moderates and Militants in Late Antique North Africa". *Journal of Late Antiquity*, 2(1)

Reference: W.H.C. Frend. "Donatus 'paene totam Africam decepit': How?"

Reference: Robert Eno. "Some Nuances in the Ecclesiology of the Donatists".

Reference: Leslie Dossey. *Peasant and Empire in Christian North Africa*. University of California Press. isbn: 978-0520254398.

Reference: Pamela Bright. *The Book of Rules of Tyconius: Its Purpose and Inner Logic*. Notre Dame Press. isbn: 978-0268012878.

Reference: Maureen Tilley. *Donatist Martyr Stories: The Church in Conflict in Roman North Africa*. Liverpool University Press. isbn: 978-0853239314.

Reference: Augustine , Maureen Tilley. *The Donatist Controversy, Vol. 1*. New City Press. isbn: 978-1565484047.

Reference: Tyconius , Francis Gumerlock X. *Exposition of the Apocalypse*. Catholic University of America Press. isbn: 978-0813229560.

Reference: Tyconius , William Babcock S.. Tyconius: The Book of Rules. Scholars Press. isbn: 978-1555403669.

Reference: Optatus , Mark Edwards. Optatus: Against the Donatists. Liverpool University Press. isbn: 978-0853237525.

Reference: Jesse Hoover. The Donatist Church in an Apocalyptic Age. Oxford University Press. isbn: 978-0198825517.

Reference: . The Donatist Schism: Controversy and Contexts. Liverpool University Press. isbn: 978-1781382813.